

Study quality assessment approach

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The need to assess the study quality for the purpose of environmental hazard assessment

Study quality – related to the quality of reporting, REDUCE risk of bias and ENSURE consistency of results, assist in determining the strength of conclusions, fit for a certain PURPOSE

Number of publications (WoS)

- Previous experience with engineered nanomaterials
- Interferences, physico-chemical properties and particle behavior impacts toxicity -> extensive information on particle properties and behavior required
- Increasing number of ecotoxicity studies with microplastics & nanoplastics -> NEED TO ASSESS THE QUALITY

Step-wise approach

Collecting existing criteria for particulates; e.g. nanomaterials

Refining existing criteria to be suited for nanoplastics & microplastics

Case study applying criteria in practice
Daphnia sp. & polystyrene nanoplastics- scientific studies

Methodology of selection, acquisition and evaluation of toxicological publications in the Project DaNa

Assessment criteria – mandatory:

PAPER

Quality evaluation of human and environmental toxicity studies performed with nanomaterials – the GUIDEnano approach

Cite this: *Environ. Sci.: Nano*, 2018, 5, 381

M. L. Fernández-Cruz, ¹ D. Hernández-Moreno, ² J. Catalán, ³ R. K. Cross, ⁴ H. Stockmann-Juviala, ⁵ J. Cabellos, ⁶ Viviana R. Lopes, ⁷ M. Matzke, ⁸ N. Ferraz, ⁹ J. J. Izquierdo, ¹⁰ J. M. Navas, ¹¹ M. Park, ¹² C. Svendsen⁹ and G. Janer¹³

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Quality of nanoplastics and microplastics ecotoxicity studies: Refining quality criteria for nanomaterial studies

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Article

Defining Quality Criteria for Nanoplastic Hazard Evaluation: The Case of Polystyrene Nanoplastics and Aquatic Invertebrate *Daphnia* spp.

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Step 1, 2- Building on 10 years of experience in the field of engineered nanomaterials

- Review of ecotoxicity scientific studies on polystyrene nanoparticles (different organisms)

Existing quality criteria for engineered nanomaterial studies

nanoCRED
DaNa criteria
GUIDEnano

Nano(micro)plastics specific study quality criteria

- ✓ Apply all criteria initially developed for other types of engineered nanomaterials
- ✓ Make a list of irrelevant criteria
- ✓ Make a **list of new nanoplastics-related criteria**

39 GUIDEnano criteria
21 DaNa criteria

New list of criteria designed specifically for nano and microplastics

1. PRIMARY PROPERTIES OF NANOPLASTICS

- 1) Polymer chemical composition
- 2) Origin of nanoplastics
- 3) Is the primary particle size stated
- 4) Is the morphology stated or graphically presented
- 5) Is the specific surface area of nanoplastics powders given
- 6) Are surface charge and chemistry described
- 7) Is the polymer density stated
- 8) Is porosity stated
- 9) Is the crystallography; phase analysis stated
- 10) Are impurities stated
- 11) Are chemical additives stated
- 12) Are other chemical pollutants stated
- 13) Other relevant information

2. ORGANISM CHARACTERIZATION AND TESTING PARAMETERS

- 14) Was the test species identified
- 15) Were any of the characteristics of the test organism stated
- 16) Was the number of replicates per group given
- 17) Was the duration of the exposure stated
- 18) Are the frequency and duration of the exposures explained
- 19) Was the type of exposure stated
- 20) Are number of concentrations and concentration range reported
- 21) Were appropriate controls used
- 22) Were parallel toxicity tests conducted with positive control
- 23) Was a reference (natural) particle used
- 24) Was the biological endpoint stated and defined
- 25) Was the biological effect quantified
- 26) Was nano(micro) plastics background verified

3. SAMPLE PREPARATION

- 27) Was the type of test medium or vehicle used stated
- 28) Were mandatory exposure medium conditions measured
- 29) Were any other exposure medium conditions measured
- 30) Were the protocols of dispersion and characterisation identified

4. NANOPLASTICS CHARACTERISTICS IN EXPOSURE MEDIUM

- 31) Is the particle behaviour described
- 32) Is the surface charge described
- 33) Is the concentration measured
- 34) Are leached chemicals from nanoplastics stated
- 35) Is the formation of the biocorona / biofouling described

5. STUDY RESULTS DOCUMENTATION

- 36) Was an appropriate statistical method or model used
- 37) Were the overload, attachment and physical effects described
- 38) Were the test acceptability criteria stated

Step 3: Case study: applying a criteria list in practice

Waterflea *Daphnia*

38 STUDIES

- 5 experts

Polystyrene NPs

[Source: 10.1021/acsomega.2c03378](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c03378)

- Specific guidance for each criterion provided

- A scoring system and threshold values for acceptance of studies/data for the purpose of hazard evaluation were developed
Mandatory, voluntary, desirable

No.	Criteria	Specific Guidance for Evaluator- Example for NanoPS	Relevance
1. Primary Properties of Nanoplastics			
1	Polymer chemical composition (CAS No)	This refers to the type of polymer, e.g., polystyrene (PS).	Mandatory
2	Origin of nanoplastics (commercial supply, laboratory production) including protocol of nanoplastic production and collection if relevant	Protocol for field collection is not relevant for primary nanoPS.	Mandatory
3	Is the primary particle size stated?	This refers to the diameter of particles.	Mandatory
4	Is the morphology (shape) stated or graphically presented?	This criterion is also valid if a microscopy image is provided. Most nanoPS are spheres and hence commonly not explicitly mentioned in studies.	Mandatory

Step 3: Case study: applying a criteria list in practice

SHARE OF STUDIES FULFILLING CRITERIA

RESULTS OF EVALUATION:

- Most of the studies passed the criteria related to test organism characterization and testing parameters, where at least 92% of all studies fulfilled the mandatory criteria
- Much lower score for primary properties of nanoplastics: - only 36 % of studies reported impurities or additives, respectively).
- Very few studies provided information on sample preparation
- **Only 18% of studies (7 out of 38) passed- fulfilling all mandatory criteria**

- The reporting of key characteristics of the test substance, organism, and test system is essential
- Criteria need refinement for other test systems, organisms & types of microplastics
- It is not feasible to assess the quality for all types of organisms/microplastics
- We suggest guidance for future studies: **minimum reporting information template** -> findability of information in documents, link to FAIR principles
- Assessing the quality is also important for other types of studies, not only ecotoxicity

We would like to acknowledge the co-authors of two publications that were used as a source material for this presentation.

Jemec Kokalj, A., Heinlaan, M., Novak, S., Drobne, D., & Kühnel, D. (2023). Defining Quality Criteria for Nanoplastic Hazard Evaluation: The Case of Polystyrene Nanoplastics and Aquatic Invertebrate *Daphnia* spp. *Nanomaterials*, 13(3),

Jemec Kokalj, A., Heinlaan, M., Novak, S., Drobne, D., & Kühnel, D. (2023). Defining Quality Criteria for Nanoplastic Hazard Evaluation: The Case of Polystyrene Nanoplastics and Aquatic Invertebrate *Daphnia* spp. *Nanomaterials*, 13(3), 536. 536.

Thank you for your attention

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